

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE EDUCATORS DURING THE PROCESS OF QUALIFIED EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE

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Abstract. *In this article, thoughts on the pedagogical and psychological factors of improving the methodology of developing the professional competences of future educators in the process of qualified educational practice are put forward. Mechanisms of development of professional competences of future educators and their role, scientific theories on their application in classes are presented.*

Keywords: *professional competence, factors, skill, qualification, training, methodological process, methodology.*

Introduction. In pre-school education organizations, with the help of examples of folk oral works told and narrated by educators and parents, and during training and non-training time, children are taught especially successfully about spiritual, moral and economic ideas on frugality, excessive spending, humanitarianism, patriotism, friendship, goodness, truthfulness, honesty, and humility. In the process of acquiring basic economic skills and competences, children acquire the ability to positively relate to people, the valuable phenomena of the surrounding reality, and respond to all bad things - laziness, selfishness, irresponsibility, indiscipline with their own opinion, it is of great educational importance to hold interesting conversations and games about treating things and objects with care [1]. In the course of these conversations, new opportunities for comprehensive use of verbal, visual and practical methods of education are opened in the process of providing children with initial economic education. In the family, the demands of parents and pedagogues-employees to acquire basic economic skills and qualifications in their relationships in the course of training will also increase.

From this age, children can easily distinguish between good and bad behavior: waste, mistreatment of objects and things, etc. However, every action, hard work, economy is necessary.

In order to properly approach personality development, it is necessary to know the nature, structure, behavior and means of influencing him [2].

In the process of arming with the initial economic concepts, only the mind and will of the pupil (in the process of organizing his activities, managing his behavior) is systematically and constantly influenced.

We have presented the pedagogical factors in our study in the following table.

Figure 1.1. Factors of providing initial economic education to preschool children

It consists of a constantly developing set of values that strives to develop our independent republic in all ways and integrate it into the world civilization.

N.Abdullayeva said that the knowledge about the past, which has been preserved in various forms for centuries, is the basis for drawing the necessary conclusions for tomorrow. The same can be said about the nation's visions of the past, national language, customs, examples of fiction in the historical genre, proverbs, epics, historical songs and other forms of folklore, spiritual, architectural monuments such as place names, national historical memory embodied in forms of material culture such as rare books, manuscripts, objects. Objectified elements of material and spiritual culture are an important source of actualization of one or another layer of national historical memory in subjective form [3].

Therefore, it is necessary for the pedagogic staff of preschool educational organizations to prepare for the process of conversations with children. Some children's interests and abilities make parents come to PEO contrary to the interests and abilities of pupils. For example, "to embarrass children who did not actively participate in the training process in front of their parents and peers".

This is very important in developing the interests and abilities of preschool children.

As a result of our research, as a result of the Variative approaches, the first economic education and the assimilation of concepts are carried out in Bulgarian pre-school education organizations after getting acquainted with numbers by teaching them to improve with coins [5].

In Polish kindergartens, there is no instruction to introduce coins in teaching first economic concepts and knowledge. However, in the specific descriptions of the activities, coins are used as calculation materials without paying attention to their value.

The US, France, England and other countries take a big place in the education of preschool children with respect to money. American pedagogues recommend focusing on the following when introducing economic concepts to children under 6 years old [4].

In order to form the first economic concepts in American kindergartens or preschool groups of school children, various didactic games "buying and selling products", as well as valuing things and products that come from labor and many tasks having a similar content are widely used. They are constantly practicing coin counting and are encouraged to work with smaller denominations.

For example, children are introduced to the concept of "profit" in the game "shop". During this game, the child is loaned money, and then he buys things from the store with this money. Then, at the suggestion of the pedagogue, the children slightly change the type of purchased items and sell these items at a higher price, children lend money from the profit and see that there are

other things. Earning money from work becomes more interesting for children, because they learn to trade and save money on their own.

In the programs of preschool educational organizations in the USA, France, England, children of preschool age are taught about money in all matters and its correct use, they learn about private property and personal savings, which are necessary in a competitive environment.

The experience of foreign countries in providing economic education to children shows that children should master not only work and all things related to it, but also product-money and monetary relations.

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